

HOW PHYSICAL VIOLENCE IN THE FAMILY AGAINST A WOMAN AFFECTS THE PERCEPTION OF HER SURROUNDING WORLD

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Physical violence - direct or indirect impact on a victim with the aim of causing physical harm, fear, pain, injury, other physical suffering or bodily harm. By using physical violence against a woman in the family, the aggressor inflicts unimaginable trauma on his victim. First of all, these are injuries, abrasions, fractures, etc. But unfortunately, these are not the only injuries that the victim receives. Mental disorders, fear of the outside world and fear of leaving such a person simply ruins women.

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In society, girls who have experienced physical violence in the family often behave very secretively, they are afraid and see a threat in every person.

Why do victims enter into such a relationship? Why can't they leave the family in which they are abused? These questions are becoming more and more popular every year. Women who were able to get out of such a marriage ceased to be silent, trying to show others through their own experience that everything is possible.

In my opinion, such a relationship attracts them from the past. Someone from childhood saw physical abuse by dad over mom, someone was insulted and humiliated at school, or she herself was an aggressor in the past. Accustomed to living in such conditions from childhood, girls subconsciously choose such life partners for themselves. For the same reason, they are often afraid to get divorced, and not even because they are not afraid for their lives. They simply cannot imagine it differently. It is addiction.

There are several signs by which your friends, colleagues or relatives can tell if they are being physically abused. The victims are usually:

- in your conversation, they express fear of their husband or are very anxious to please him;

- follow all his instructions;
- they always call and write to their spouse in order to tell them where they are and what they are doing;

- receive too frequent calls or messages from their husband;
- talk about jealousy and a feeling of ownership in the spouse.

There are also some psychological signs that should alert you:

- very low self-esteem;
- drastic changes in personality;
- increased anxiety, depression, talking, or attempted suicide;
- they constantly wear closed clothes and hide their face and eyes in every possible way, even indoors.

How can we help? You need to follow a simple algorithm of possible actions:

- talk to a woman in private;
- ask if something happened in her life and specifically in the family;
- Explain what exactly worries you about the person;
- if the victim is not ready to share and talk about this, make it clear that you are there and are ready to listen and help at any time;
- make sure that everything said remains between you;
- offer her your help.

According to experts, you shouldn't do the following:

- wait for the victim to turn to you for help;
- blame someone;
- put pressure on her.

What will be the perception of the world around a woman who is physically abused in the family? She often does not reach any heights at work, or she simply does not develop in those directions that she likes. He behaves very secretively, is afraid of communication with other men and avoids him in every possible way. In terms of motherhood, she also cannot fully fulfill her functions (the model of physical violence has a very detrimental effect on the child, as they grow up, they very often adopt the behavior of their parents and live the same life). Such women pale against the background of the rest.

Summing up, I want to emphasize the importance of the topic of violence. It is very important to create centers that help to get out of such a relationship. Raise such topics on social networks, television, radio. Provide psychological assistance to victims, because there are many known cases of suicide. To say that

our life is the most valuable thing we have and no one has the right to decide how we should live it, let alone deprive it. I believe that if each of us thinks about this topic more globally and even tries to do something a little, the world will change for the better and very soon women will stop being afraid to talk about it and will start making decisions and fighting.

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